

Paper 2

A STUDY ON PORTRAYAL OF LGBTQ (LESBIAN, GAY, BISEXUAL, TRANSGENDER, QUEER) IN INDIAN WEB SERIES AND ADVERTISEMENTS

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ABSTRACT

The world has witnessed several shifts in technology and mass media. Media consumption has become vital in today’s society. Dependency on media has been increasing with every new innovation. From radios to television and television to the internet, we have come a long way. Media is surely a powerful tool in today’s world that is powerful enough to change the perceptions of the masses. In this study we look into the ability of the web-based media and advertisements to change the society’s perceptions about the LGBTQ.

A decade ago, LGBTQ representation used to be sidelined from receiving lead roles in Television, Tv shows and Films. Even if there were any portrayals, they would be shown in a negative light. However, due to the recent developments, the LGBTQ movements have sparked a nationwide attention. This has resulted in the shift of LGBTQ portrayals on media. There have been many Films, Web series and Advertisements featuring LGBTQ lead characters. The current study is aimed to specifically identify and analyze some popular web series and advertisements that have LGBTQ portrayals. Additionally, have a dialog with the individuals from the LGBTQ community to check their views on the LGBTQ portrayal on these Web Series and Advertisements.

Keywords: LGBTQ, Web Series, Advertisements, Homophobia, Stereotyping

Introduction

Media has always been a powerful tool in changing perception of the masses. For several decades social scientists have been theorizing its impact on the people who consume it. One such example can be taken from the era of world war, where Hitler made extensive use of the mass media to

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propagate hatred towards the Jews. Pro- Nazi films were made to convince the audience that resulted in mass execution of Jews. Those are days when radio, television and newspapers were used to disseminate information to the masses. Motion picture on the other hand has also been a means of entertainment. Along with entertainment, certain movies have been known to change the viewers perception. Today, we have the internet which has become the popular mode of spreading information. The internet has paved way to new contents such as the Web series. Web series is a new form of storytelling which has been gaining traction through both online and television. High speed internet services have paved way for these web series to enter India.

Gender has always been a social construct. Since childhood, one has been taught of only two genders, male and female. However, the existence of the third gender has always been sidelined. To understand this study, one must need to understand the fundamentals of gender studies. Often in the academic arena, we see sex linked with biology and gender as a term linked with a society and its culture. Commonly, we take ‘sex’ of an individual to create the socially perceived ‘gender’ of that individual. The sexuality of an individual is assumed based on the sexual orientation or the sexual inclinations of an individual. Though it has a historical background linking to scriptures such as the ‘*Manusmruthi*’. There are several mentions in antient writings where individuals have been swapping their genders. For several centuries, there have been several debates among the intellects over the connection between the self and the body. Many such identities still exist among us such as the *Hijras* in India, the *Muxes* in Mexico, or *Kathoeys* in Thiland. Same sex relationship is not a new concept. There are enough evidences to prove its existence in ancient Roman and Greek civilizations. It was a part of the elite culture and was a behavior that was socially acceptable. There were also several Greek Gods who indulged in same sex relations. Such sexual practices were also observed in ancient Egyptian civilization. During the Ottoman Empire in late Turkey 1858, same-sexual activity was legalized. Though homosexuality and asexuality are allowed in the country today, it still stands second in Europe for being the most restrictive country for LGBTQ laws and policies (**Ince Yenilmez, 2020**). Thus, we know that same sex relationships have history that dates back to several civilizations.

The individuals who contradict the biological binary are categorized as the LGBTQ (Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Transgender, Queer). The term Lesbianism relates to sexual behavior from one female to another female or same-sex attraction between females. Gay refers to a homosexual trait where

there is a sexual attraction between members of the same gender. Whereas, Bisexuality refers to the sexual behavior or attraction towards more than one gender or sex. Transgenders are when individuals of a certain gender or identity that differs from their assigned sex during birth **(Ince Yenilmez, 2020)**.

Radical theorization of sexual identities has a fairly short background. Lessening sexuality to just reproduction will totally be a narrow view. Freud didn't envision the sexual charisma as instinctually situated towards procreative, genital heterosexuality yet rather towards polymorphous delights – and, that is something that is frequently considered presently to be a radical view **(Kumar, 2018)**. For decades the LGBTQ individuals have been facing violence, discrimination and rejection from the society. The social system and archaic laws have been suppressing the LGBTQ community for centuries. These stringent laws caused a lot of these individuals from revealing their gender identity. The emergence of movies, television series and social media and its use of LGBTQ characters has changed the perceptions of viewers over time. Only recently, we see a lot of individuals from these groups emerge and fight for their legal rights. The world has been seen embracing the LGBTQ community slowly. From being criminalized to being portrayed as socially misfits, the attitudes towards the Homosexuals have begun to change rapidly over the years in many countries including developing countries. Permits allowing gay marriage are given in some countries, which is an evidence of changing attitudes towards the LGBTQ **(Hoel, Lewis, Einarsdottir, 2021)**. Popular forms of media such as Movies, Television shows, Advertisements and magazines have become the prime source through which youngsters learn about their society and the world around them. These media play a role in altering attitudes and beliefs as shown in media expressions to understand their sense of identity. These Popular media have impact on youngsters who continually immerse themselves with media content that overgeneralize portrayals of different social groups specifically the gay and lesbian stereotypes. Hence it appears that the media has influence in persuading the audience to think in a certain way. Thereof, the current research paper is aimed to study the Indian web series that show LGBTQ characters and its influence on young viewers.

Review of Literature

A Historical backdrop on LGBTQ

Though homosexuality was seen as age old practices in several ancient civilizations, we witness

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laws against homosexuality in today’s political landscape. The reason for this can be traced back to strong influences of teachings from the Church and the age-old laws of the British society. This is one reason why we see its influence in our Indian judicial system. These laws when coupled with western beliefs have directly or indirectly impacted on the public acceptance of homosexuality. The anti-LGBT laws and policies side discrimination and force the LGBTQ individuals to stay invisible in the society (**John, 2018**).

Many countries do not consider abuses against LGBTQ individuals as human rights violations. While certain countries such as Iran and Saudi Arabia have laws that call for execution of individuals practicing homosexuality. A study by Clinton Glenn reveals the discrimination faced by the gay individuals by the homophobic government in Russia. The “gay propaganda bill” that was passed in 2013 was signed by President Vladimir Putin, which put a ban on the promotion of sexual practices that were nontraditional, which was under the guise of protecting the children (**Glenn, 2020**). About 40 countries still consider same sex behavior as a criminal offence for both men and women and around 35 countries criminalize the behavior only for men (**Marks, 2006**). There are arguments that laws made on homosexuality by countries, their modernization and de-traditionalization process and religious practices and beliefs have an impact on the attitudes towards homosexuality in whole (**Witte, Iterbeke, & Holz, 2019**). A study on EU LGBT that took place in 2014 revealed that the majority of lesbian, gay, bisexual and transgenders felt discrimination in the field of education and employment, which kept them from experiencing the fundamental rights and often encountered violence and harassment (**European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights, 2014**). Be that as it may, across Africa, the homosexual groups keep on confronting physical and rhetorical dangers. The greater part of this setback comes from government and strict religious leaders who point out that foreign, pro homosexual practices are spreading across the mainland. Accordingly, governments often control the media to restrict those ideas or thoughts and stall the openness towards positive LGBTQ representation (**Winkler, 2019**).

Stereotyping of Women

Gender stereotyping has been seen on several platforms including platforms in media that shows strong gender stereotyped superhero characters that show masculinity. Studies show children being exposed to male-stereotyped shows that promotes weapon play. The media tends to depict solid gender stereotypes for both girls and boys. As indicated by the social cognitive theory of gender development, seeing sex cliché conduct in the media can impact playing habits in kids. This

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hypothesis proposes that behavioral outcomes, like play, are crucially significant for both exploring and practicing gender roles. Studies point out that the television viewing habits can reinforce or develop the attitudes of children regarding the stereotyping of gender. Mayes and Valentine characterized gender-role stereotypes as assortments of gender-specific attributes or conventional standards that differentiate average feminine attributes from average masculine attributes in the society. Undoubtedly, the more TV kids watch, the more stereotypical they are when it comes to gendered personality traits, domestic activities, career, and the almost certain they are to accept that men hold an upper status than women **(Coynne, Linder, Rasmussen, Nelson, & Collier, 2014)**. According to a study by Hertz-Tang and Carnes, there are various factors at workspace that prevent women from getting leadership posts. Both women and men are equally effective in becoming leaders and might be sometimes more likely than men to show ground-breaking instead of transactional leadership. There are plenty of evidences where women have performed exceptionally well where they could enhance operational performance and recruiting ability. But they often face overt and subtle biases based on the gender stereotypes which keep them from achieving their professional goals or leadership positions **(Hertz-Tang & Carnes, 2020)**. Another study points out the feminine attributes that are usually associated with women being compassionate and communal, on the contrary the attributes of men being independent and dominating. This male-female stereotypes, discrimination, and gender role expectations make it harder for women to achieve entrepreneurial success **(Bullough, Guelich, Manolova, & Schjoedt , 2021)**.

Stereotyping of LGBTQ

After exploring the stereotyping of women, we look into the stereotyping of the LGBTQ. The Lesbian, Gay and Bisexual workers often face further risks at a work setup. They confront harsh forms of bullying and social exclusion **(Hoel, Lewis, Einarsdottir, 2021)**.

Gender Studies

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), *“Gender is used to describe the characteristics of women and men that are socially constructed, while sex refers to those that are biologically determined. People are born female or male, but learn to be girls and boys who grow into women and men. This learned behaviour makes up gender identity and determines gender roles.”* **(WHO, 2002)**.

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Role of Films and Documentaries

Films and documentaries played a key role in envisioning human rights for the global LGBT communities. Film makers joined hands with human rights activists and community partners and engaged in transforming the societies through films in Africa, India and the Caribbean. Those movies that are thoroughly instilled with predominant ideology are classified "dominant films" and the one that assault the dominant ideology are designated "resistant films". These films oppose the dominant discourses on queer and other sexual identities (**Labade, 2016**). The documentaries were able to tell stories, investigate human rights violations and advocate for social justice to the LGBTQ individuals (**Nicol, 2018**). On the other hand, there have been several Film Festivals dedicated to LGBTQ themes. An example for this is the Inside out LGBT Film and Video festival which was formerly known as Gay and Lesbian Film and Video Festival, which is a nonprofit charitable organization that aims at promoting, producing and exhibiting of films that have LGBT themes. This festival targets to challenge the attitudes and change the lives of its viewers who attend the screenings (**Pereira, 2013**). Jeffrey Hawkins in his study points out an observation made by Stephen Jimenez who is an educational equity compliance specialist for the Los Angeles Unified School District, educators struggle to integrate the LGBTQ problems in their curriculum and debate about those in class. Hence, they take aid of visual mediums such as films that have the LGBTQ themes as class demonstrations (**Hawkins, 2017**).

Role of Web series

The advent of internet, latest streaming and advanced compression techniques have allowed Netflix, an online DVD rental company, that allows consumers to access movies and Tv programs at their homes through the use of Internet (**Cheng, Feng, Koehler, Marston, 2011**). Web series or web television is a new genre in digital entertainment which began in United States of America during mid-1990s. this is when viewers started using digital technologies to propound their control on cultural flows (**Monaghan, 2017**). Web series are also believed to include content that are usually sidelined by the mainstream media. Besides, it gives particular importance to marginalized individuals such as the LGBTQ who barely get represented on screen (**Monaghan, pp.164**).

Most of the earlier social science researches focused on general attitudes of the people towards homosexuality, or the influence of homosexuality at workplace, attitudes of pre-service teachers and homonegativity in higher education (**Witte, Iterbeke, & Holz, 2019**).

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Viewers / Audience

The Popular Medias like films, television shows, advertisements and magazines have become the most prime source of information through which children learn about others and their surroundings. This shapes their attitudes and beliefs as portrayed in these media expressions, and then conclude their sense of gender identity. Children are constantly seen immersed in these media vehicles that mostly perpetuate generalized representations of different cultural groups, specially the gay and lesbian stereotypes (**Chung, 2007**).

Rationale /research gap

Over the years several social scientists have been trying to theorize the effects of mass media on its consumers. Several studies have been conducted on the effects of films, advertisements that change the consumers perceptions. However, web series being a new form of media, an approach to study its impact on consumers must be made. Despite of countless efforts that go into research in media convergence, very little scholarly attention goes into the study of web series. However, this study only focuses on the portrayal of LGBTQ individuals in web series and its impact on young audience.

Objectives

1. To study the representation of LGBTQ in Indian Web Series
2. To study the representation of LGBTQ in Indian Advertisements
3. To explore the perception of the LGBTQ about the representation in the Indian Web series

Methodology

- This study comes under Developmental Research as it addresses global and local inequality also in particular Gender inequality.
- There is a growing interest in Developmental studies as various studies reveal inequality as an important factor leading to poverty and distress in various countries.
- The following research would require a multi-method approach.
- In depth interviews of individuals from the LGBTQ communities.

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